

PROCESSING WARPAGE OF ASYMMETRIC COMPOSITE PANELS MANUFACTURED BY RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING

P. Causse^{1*}, E. Ruiz¹, F. Trochu¹

¹ Chaire sur les Composites à Haute Performance (CCHP), École Polytechnique de Montréal, C.P. 6079, Station Centre-ville, Montréal (Québec), H3C 3A7, Canada

* Corresponding author (philippe.causse@polymtl.ca)

Keywords: *Resin Transfer Molding, residual distortion, numerical modeling*

1 Introduction

Residual distortion can be a strong impediment for the use of thermoset composites in high performance applications. Over the past decades, numerical models based on the finite element method have thus been proposed to simulate internal stresses developed during autoclave processing [1-3] or in Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) [4-6]. In the latter case, the injection stage is generally neglected by considering that the degree of cure and temperature are initially uniform throughout the part. The objective of the present study is to test the validity of this assumption by investigating the potential effect of the filling stage on residual deformations.

2 Preliminary Experimental Observations

2.1 Manufacturing Experiments

Composite specimens were manufactured with an RTM mold that was already available in our laboratory. This setup was designed to manufacture flat panel of dimensions 400×142 mm. The tooling consists of two aluminum parts having a thickness of 20 mm for the top mold and 50 mm for the lower mold. The mold is equipped with electrical heating plates that allow high temperature manufacturing. Materials were quasi-unidirectional glass fiber fabric and a regular epoxy system (DGEBA cured with an anhydride hardener). An asymmetric stacking sequence [0 0 90 90] was selected to induce an important distortion that could be easily measured. A typical part is shown in Fig. 1. Processing experiments were conducted with a mold temperature of 140°C. Resin was injected at room temperature under a constant injection pressure of 0.1 MPa.

2.2 Analysis of Distortion

After demolding, each panel was cut along its length into several smaller specimens of dimensions 180×20 mm. The samples were polished with waterproof sandpaper to acquire clean images of the cut surfaces with a scanner CanoScan 5600F having a resolution of 2400 dpi. These images were then treated with Matlab to calculate the curvature along the longitudinal direction. Results showed that the curvature in the second half of the panel (i.e. close to the vent port) was about 4% greater than in the first half of the part (i.e. close to the inlet). Though relatively small, this difference was observed on all five parts analyzed and could be a result of the filling of the cavity since it coincides with the injection direction.

3 Numerical Analysis of Filling and Cure

Anisotropic thermal expansion and cure shrinkage are the two main factors responsible for the internal stress built-up. These phenomena are governed by the evolution of the degree of cure and temperature during processing. Consequently, non-isothermal simulations of both filling and curing stages were conducted to analyze the influence of injection conditions on the thermochemical history of the composite. These numerical analyses were performed with the software PAM-RTM.

3.1 Modeling

A parametric 2D finite element model of the manufacturing setup was developed using triangular elements in the cavity region and quadrilateral elements for both halves of the mold. This model was used to predict the evolution of the degree of cure and temperature during injection under constant pressure followed by a 10 minute-period of curing. Since the cycle time was relatively short, adiabatic

boundary conditions were imposed during the entire simulation.

Despite the asymmetry of the layup, a constant permeability of $1.4 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$ was considered for the fiber bed. The viscosity of the resin was modeled according to the following power law:

$$\eta = \frac{a}{T^b} \quad (1)$$

where a and b are two fitting parameters reported in Table 1. The viscosity η and the temperature are expressed in Pa.s and °C respectively.

Cure reaction was described with the well-known Kamal-Sourour kinetics model [7]:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dT} = (K_1 + K_2 \cdot \alpha^m) \cdot (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (2)$$

with rate constants K_i following Arrhenius law:

$$K_i = A_i \exp\left(-\frac{E_i}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

Parameters of the kinetics model are summarized in Table 1. A total heat of reaction of 326 J.g^{-1} was determined by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Other materials properties involved in the numerical analyses are reported in Table 2.

The first simulation was conducted with the processing parameters used during the manufacture of the test specimens:

- part length $L = 0.4 \text{ m}$;
- part thickness $h = 3.8 \text{ mm}$;
- fiber volume fraction $V_f = 40\%$;
- mold temperature $T_{mold} = 140^\circ\text{C}$;
- resin injection temperature $T_{resin} = 30^\circ\text{C}$;
- mold made of aluminum.

As will be presented in the next section, results obtained with such processing conditions were used as a reference case to conduct parametric studies.

Fig. 2 shows contour plots of the temperature and degree of cure predicted 80 seconds after the end of the filling stage. As can be seen, injecting a resin that is much colder than the mold can result in significant temperature and cure gradients in the cavity. In the case presented here, the cure reaction is already advanced in the end part of the panel and the exothermic nature of the reaction induces a temperature increase in the region close to vent port. On the other hand, the temperature of the mold is

lower near the inlet gate because of cooling induced by the injection process and the degree of cure is still almost negligible at this location.

The results presented in Fig. 2 does not necessarily mean that residual stresses vary throughout the part. Indeed, the existence of in-plane properties gradients at a certain time could simply be due to a time lag in the evolution of the reaction between the different regions of the composite. To investigate this point, the degree of cure was plotted versus temperature as reported in Fig. 3. The latter clearly shows that thermal and cure histories vary inside the cavity. The effect is more important in the vicinity of the injection gate, notably during the early stages of the polymerization reaction. Moreover, the exothermic peaks occur for similar degrees of cure but are associated with different maximum temperatures. Such differences in the thermochemical history suggest that the combined evolution of mechanical properties and volumetric changes is not uniform inside the cavity. This can in turn modify the development of internal stresses during the fabrication.

3.2 Parametric Studies

Many processing parameters can affect cure and thermal histories experienced by the composite. To illustrate this point, some selected numerical results are presented in the following subsections.

3.2.1 Influence of Part Dimensions

As shown in Fig. 4a, the predicted thermochemical history is fairly uniform when the length of the part is reduced to 0.2 m. Minor variations only exist for low degree of cure and should not affect the level of stresses since the resin is still liquid at that moment. On the other hand, a part length of 0.8 m generates larger variations compared to the reference case. Note that for sake of clarity, results are only presented for the first half of the panel in Fig. 4b. The thermochemical history becomes much more uniform when the distance from the inlet is higher than 0.4 m (although small variation are still predicted).

Increasing the length of the part results in a larger quantity of injected resin and consequently a more important cooling effect near the inlet gate. Fig. 5 shows that a similar behavior is predicted when the thickness of the part varies. While no significant difference is seen with a thickness of 2 mm,

increasing this parameter to 8 mm induces important variations of the thermochemical history compared to the reference test. Note that the scale of the temperature axis in Fig. 5b is larger than the one used in Fig. 3 to 5a because of the important exothermic peak caused by the increased thickness.

3.2.2 Influence of Injection Temperature

A rather intuitive solution for decreasing in-plane cure and temperature gradients consists of increasing the resin temperature. Indeed, a lower temperature difference between the resin and the mold should reduce the intensity of heat transfer phenomena during the injection stage. This is confirmed by the simulation results presented in Fig. 6. As can be seen, increasing resin temperature to 100°C gives in a fairly uniform thermochemical history throughout the part. However, it must be kept in mind that such experiment may not be easy to conduct in practice. For highly reactive thermoset systems like the one used in this study, a complex injection machine with on-line mixing or efficient heat exchanger would be necessary to avoid premature gel of the resin. The use of such device will inevitably increase the costs of process implementation.

3.2.3 Influence of Mold Material

It is well-known that the material used for the tooling can substantially affect residual stresses and distortion. For example, a material with low thermal expansion such as invar may be used to decrease the level of tool/part interaction occurring during processing. However, changing the mold material also modifies other thermal properties that dictate the evolution of temperature and degree of cure in the cavity. This point is supported by Fig. 7, which plots the thermochemical history predicted with a tool made of invar (all other parameters are identical to the reference test). In this case, important variations are predicted in the immediate vicinity of the inlet. The cooling effect of resin injection is indeed much more localized because of the low thermal conductivity of invar compared to aluminum (see Table 2). This difference in thermal properties also induces an increase of the maximum temperature because the tooling is a less efficient heat sink to absorb the energy generated by the reaction.

4 Prediction of Process-Induced Stresses and Distortion

To simulate the development of residual stresses during cure, a second finite element model was developed with the ABAQUS software. This model only included the composite panel (the manufacturing tool was not considered). Thermomechanical analyses of the manufacturing cycle were divided into three simulation steps:

- curing stage;
- cooling down to 30°C;
- demolding of the part.

Fixed boundary conditions were imposed during both curing and cooling stages whereas the part was let free to deform during the demolding step. The main originality of the model consists of transferring the simulation results obtained with PAM-RTM to represent the thermochemical history during curing. By doing so, the prediction of residual stresses takes into account the possible influence of the mold filling stage.

4.1 Transfer of Cure Simulation Results

Both temperature and degree of cure predicted during the curing step were used as predefined variables imposed on nodes in the thermomechanical simulations performed with ABAQUS. To facilitate the transfer of these fields, each quadrilateral element used in ABAQUS correspond to four triangular elements in the PAM-RTM mesh. Temperature was directly transferred from node to node. In the case of degree of cure, the output results of PAM-RTM are given at elements. To convert these data to nodal variables, results were averaged for all the elements connected to a single node.

4.2 Material Modeling

Accurately predicting manufacturing stresses is a difficult task that require the use of sophisticated material laws for mechanical properties and volumetric changes. However, since the goal our work is to determine if injection conditions can impact the residual distortion, relatively simple models were selected to describe the composite behavior in order to simplify the numerical implementation and avoid extensive material characterization. Such approach should not be recommended to make reliable quantitative

predictions and was only used to detect possible qualitative trends in the results.

4.2.1 Resin Properties

The epoxy used in this study was previously characterized by Ruiz et al. [8]. These authors observed that the resin started to develop significant rigidity for a degree of cure of 33%. This value was then considered to correspond to the gel point of the matrix. The degree of cure at gel α_{gel} notably plays a role in the modeling of chemical shrinkage, which was represented by a linear relationship:

$$\left(\frac{1}{V_0} \frac{dV}{dt} \right)_{chem} = \frac{S_{tot}}{1 - \alpha_{gel}} \frac{d\alpha}{dt} \quad (4)$$

The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the fully cured resin was characterized with a thermomechanical analyzer. The results shown in Fig. 8 were used to derive the following model for the linear CTE of the matrix:

$$CTE_m = CTE_1 + \frac{CTE_2 - CTE_1}{1 + \exp\left(\frac{T - T_g + T'}{D}\right)} \quad (5)$$

where CTE_1 and CTE_2 are the coefficients of thermal expansion in the rubbery and glassy state, T' and D are fitting parameters and the glass transition T_g varies with the degree of cure according to DiBenedetto equation [9]:

$$\frac{T_g - T_g^0}{T_g^\infty - T_g^0} = \frac{\lambda \alpha}{1 - (1 - \lambda)\alpha} \quad (6)$$

A similar approach was used to represent the influence of temperature and reaction advancement on the mechanical properties of the resin. Young's modulus of the resin was thus expressed as:

$$E_m = E_1 + \frac{E_2 - E_1}{1 + \exp\left(\frac{T - T_g + T'}{D}\right)} \quad (7)$$

where typical values were assumed for the rubbery and glassy moduli E_1 and E_2 . The mechanical model was completed by assuming a constant Poisson's ratio ν_m . These properties as well as others parameters involved in equations 4 to 7 are summarized in Table 3.

4.2.2 Homogenization of composite properties

Simple analytical formulas were used to predict the evolution of the composite properties during cure. The resin models described above and constant fiber properties (see Table 3) were used as input data. The elastic constants were calculated according to Chamis model [10]. The different CTEs were estimated with the equations proposed by Schapery [11]. These expressions were also used to calculate the orthotropic chemical shrinkage experienced by the composite. The micromechanics equations and the different material models were implemented in ABAQUS via user-programmed subroutines UMAT and UEXPAN. To avoid predicting any residual stresses when the resin is still liquid, the CTE and cure shrinkage of the resin were considered to be zero for degree of cure lower than α_{gel} .

4.3 Results

Fig. 9 shows the longitudinal stress profiles predicted prior to demolding for the reference test. As can be seen, the stresses are not constant throughout the panel. However, the relative changes are very small and this non-uniform stress state is expected to induce only minor variations of residual distortion once the part is demolded. Consequently, these numerical results suggest that the injection does not play a significant role on the residual stresses and deformations for this specific case. However, this conclusion should not be extended to a more general context. Firstly, the reference specimen is rather small and much larger structures can be manufactured for real applications. For example, increasing the length of the part to 0.8 m results in larger predicted stress variations as shown in Fig. 10. Secondly, using a mold material with low thermal conductivity is expected to induce important stress gradients in the inlet region as illustrated in Fig. 11. Thirdly, it should be reminded that residual warpage of asymmetric laminates is mainly due to thermal stresses developing during cooling when the resin is in the glassy state [12]. For curved geometries, distortion could be more sensitive to variations of the thermochemical history when the resin is in the rubbery state.

5 Conclusion

This study investigated the impact of the injection stage on the residual stresses and deformations induced by RTM manufacturing. The work was motivated by preliminary experimental observations showing some variations of process-induced warpage along the injection direction of asymmetric flat panels. To investigate this behavior, non-isothermal filling and cure simulation were first conducted with PAM-RTM. Results showed that the evolution of degree of cure and temperature during processing could be influenced by the initial state resulting from the injection step. Factors such as part geometry, mold material and injection temperature notably influence the variations of the thermochemical history.

Thermomechanical finite element analyses were conducted by transferring the results of filling and cure simulations to the standard commercial software ABAQUS. This sequential model allowed to consider the injection stage in the prediction of manufacturing stresses and distortion. Results show stress gradients that could not be predicted without taking into account the injection step. However, work is still needed to conclude about the necessity of adopting such approach. Future studies on this subject could investigate the possible impact of tool/part interaction and use more sophisticated material models. Further investigation will also require the use of adapted experimental techniques in order to detect small local variations of manufacturing distortion.

Table 1. Viscosity and cure kinetics model parameters.

A	15918
B	3.1
A_1 (s ⁻¹)	0.133
E_1 (J.mol ⁻¹)	5080
A_2 (s ⁻¹)	8.5
E_2 (J.mol ⁻¹)	6630
n	1.5
m	1.42

Table 2. Summary of materials thermal properties

	Density (kg.m ⁻³)	Specific heat (J.kg ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹)	Conductivity (W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹)
Fibers	2600	700	1
Resin	1160	1110	0.25
Aluminum	2700	900	237
Invar	8125	510	13

Table 3. Summary of materials properties used in the thermomechanical analysis

Resin properties					
S_{tot} (%)	3.2	α_{gel}	0.33		
CTE_1 (K ⁻¹)	191×10^{-6}	CTE_2 (K ⁻¹)	70×10^{-6}		
E_1 (MPa)	30	E_2 (GPa)	3	ν_m	0.3
T^* (°C)	12.6	D (°C)	4.8		
T_g^0 (°C)	-35	T_g^∞ (°C)	137	λ	0.4
Fiber properties					
E_f (GPa)	73	ν_f	0.2	CTE_f (K ⁻¹)	5×10^{-6}

Fig.1. Asymmetric composite panel manufactured by RTM.

Fig.2. Predicted temperature and degree of cure 80 seconds after filling for the reference test.

Fig.3. Predicted thermochemical history for the reference test.

Fig.4. Influence of part length on the predicted thermochemical history: (a) $L=0.2$ m ; (b) $L=0.8$ m.

Fig.5. Influence of part thickness on the predicted thermochemical history.

Fig.6. Predicted thermochemical history with an injection temperature of 100°C .

Fig.7. Predicted thermochemical history with an invar tooling.

Fig.10. Predicted longitudinal stresses before demolding with a part length of 0.8 m.

Fig.8. Thermal expansion behavior of the fully cured resin.

Fig.11. Predicted longitudinal stresses before demolding with an invar tooling.

Fig.9. Predicted longitudinal stresses before demolding for the reference test.

References

- [1] A. Johnston, R. Vaziri and A. Poursartip “A plane strain model for process-induced deformation of laminated composite structures”. *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 35, No. 16, pp 1435-1469, 2001.
- [2] Q. Zhu, P. H. Li and C. L. Tucker III “Dimensional accuracy of thermoset composites: simulation of process-induced residual stresses”. *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 35, No. 24, pp 2171-2205, 2001.
- [3] X. Zeng and J. Raghavan “role of tool-part interaction in process-induced warpage of autoclave-manufactured composite structures”. *Composites Part A*, Vol. 41, No. 9, pp 1174-1183, 2010.

- [4] H. Golestanian and A. S. El-Gizawy “Modeling of process induced residual stresses in resin transfer molded composite parts with woven fiber mats”. *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 35, No. 17, pp 1513-1528, 2001.
- [5] J. M. Svanberg, C. Altkvist and T. Nyman “Prediction of shape distortions for a curved composite C-spar”. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol. 24, No. 3, pp 323-339, 2005.
- [6] L. Khoun and P. Hubert “Investigation of the dimensional stability of carbon epoxy cylinders manufactured by resin transfer molding”. *Composites Part A*, Vol. 41, No. 1, pp 116-124, 2010.
- [7] M. R. Kamal “Thermoset characterization for moldability analysis”. *Polymer Engineering and Science*, Vol. 14, No. 3, pp 231-239, 1974.
- [8] E. Ruiz, C. Billotte, F. Morin Bernard, F. Cara and H. Baurier “Chemical and thermomechanical characterization of an epoxy resin during cure by a novel in situ measurement method”. *Proceedings of 18th International Conference on Composite Materials*, Jeju Island, Korea, 2011.
- [9] A. T. DiBenedetto “Prediction of the glass transition temperature of polymers: a model based on the principle of corresponding states” *Journal of Polymer Science, Part B: Polymer Physics*, Vol. 25, No. 9, pp 1949-1969, 1987.
- [10] C.C. Chamis “Simplified composite micromechanics equations for hygral, thermal and mechanical properties”. *NASA Technical Memorandum*, 1983.
- [11] R. A. Schapery “Thermal expansion coefficients of composite materials based on energy principles”. *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 2, No. 3, pp 380-403.
- [12] N. Ersoy, K. Potter, M. R. Wisnom and M. J. Clegg “Development of spring-in angle during cure of a thermosetting composite”. *Composites Part A*, Vol. 36, No. 12, pp 1700-1706, 2005